

A Study on Employee Engagement with Reference to Employees of Small Manufacturing Companies in Dadra and Nagar Haveli and Vapi

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Employee engagement is one of the most essential aspects of human resource management as it directly influences productivity, motivation, and employee retention. The present study focuses on understanding the level of employee engagement in a small manufacturing company located in the Dadra and Nagar Haveli and Vapi region. The objectives of this study are to understand the concept and importance of employee engagement, analyse engagement practices adopted by the organization, and assess employees' satisfaction with current initiatives. The study is descriptive in nature and uses primary data collected through a structured questionnaire from 117 employees. The results show that most employees are satisfied with communication, support, and participation in management decisions. The study concludes that employee engagement is a continuous process that needs regular attention to maintain a motivated and loyal workforce.

Keywords: employee engagement, motivation, job satisfaction, HR practices, organizational growth

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1. Introduction

Employee engagement refers to the level of enthusiasm, commitment, and emotional investment employees exhibit toward their work and organization. Beyond job satisfaction, engagement represents a meaningful connection with one's role, impacting productivity, performance, and organizational success. The present study was conducted to understand the level of engagement among employees in a small manufacturing company, the factors influencing their engagement, and their satisfaction with current engagement practices.

1.1 Problem Statement

In the DNH and Vapi region, manufacturing companies employ a large workforce, often in monotonous roles with limited advancement opportunities. This may lead to disengagement, absenteeism, and high attrition, negatively affecting company profitability and sustainability. This study aims to analyse current engagement practices, assess their effectiveness, and provide recommendations to improve employee satisfaction and retention.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

1. To study the concept and importance of employee engagement in organizational success.
2. To analyse engagement practices in small manufacturing companies.
3. To assess employee satisfaction with current engagement initiatives.

2. Significance of the Study

For Organizations:

- Enhances productivity and reduces absenteeism
- Lowers turnover and associated costs
- Promotes a positive organizational culture
- Improves overall profitability

For Employees:

- Increases job satisfaction and morale
- Supports career growth and training opportunities
- Enhances work-life balance

For HR and Business Leaders:

- Guides strategic decision-making
- Improves leadership communication and motivation strategies
- Supports data-driven HR practices for employee retention

3. Literature Review

A review of previous research helps in understanding how different scholars and practitioners have studied employee engagement and what factors influence it.

Tomar (2019) investigates employee engagement across ten Indian business sectors, emphasizing how organizational effectiveness and people-centric practices vary by industry. His findings show that engagement is not uniform it depends on sector-specific dynamics such as work culture, leadership style, and employee expectations.

Gupta et al. (2015) focus on the financial services offshoring sector, identifying three key engagement drivers: implicit benefits (like job security and global exposure), organizational culture, and HR policies. Their qualitative approach highlights how engagement is shaped by the nature of outsourced work and employee perceptions of value.

Markos & Sridevi (2010) offer a foundational definition of employee engagement, describing it as a blend of emotional and cognitive involvement. They argue that engaged employees are more productive, loyal, and innovative. Their work is widely cited and sets the tone for understanding engagement as a strategic HR priority.

Kasinathan & Rajee (2019) reinforce this view by showing how leadership, communication, and recognition directly influence engagement levels. Their study, though general, supports the idea that engagement is a key factor in employee retention and performance.

Shrotryia & Dhanda (2020) address a major gap in the literature the lack of a consistent measurement framework. Using grounded theory and interviews with leaders from India's best companies to work for, they develop a multi-dimensional engagement tool. This framework includes emotional, cognitive, and behavioural components, offering a practical way to assess engagement.

Rai & Yadav (2022) take a conceptual approach, redefining engagement as a dynamic and evolving construct. They emphasize psychological ownership, emotional commitment, and the changing expectations of employees in modern Indian firms. Their work is especially relevant for understanding engagement in younger, tech-savvy workforces.

Deepa lakshmi et al. (2024) explore how engagement contributes to organizational outcomes like innovation, customer satisfaction, and retention. They use HR theories to show that leadership style, feedback mechanisms, and supportive culture are essential for sustaining engagement.

Bhowal & Sain (2019) provide practical strategies for Indian firms, focusing on leadership, communication, and work-life balance. Their recommendations are grounded in real-world HR practices and offer actionable insights for managers seeking to improve engagement.

4. Research Methodology

Research methodology refers to the systematic plan and approach used to conduct research. It encompasses the methods, techniques, and procedures employed to gather, analyse, and interpret data. The methodology provides the framework that guides the entire research process, ensuring the findings are valid, reliable, and scientifically sound.

Research Methodology

Topic	A study on employment engagement
Research Design	Descriptive
Sample population	Employees of the company
Sample Size	117 sample size of employees
No. of Questions	11
Sampling technique	Snowball and Convenience
Research instrument	A survey method
Analysis tools & Methods	Percentage Analysis

5. Data Analysis

Data analysis is a critical step in research that involves organizing, summarizing, and interpreting collected data to draw meaningful insights. In this study, data analysis focuses on understanding employee engagement practices in a small manufacturing company in Dadra and Nagar Haveli (DNH) and Vapi.

Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire from 117 employees, and the responses were analyzed using percentage analysis to identify trends, patterns, and key findings. The analysis provides insights into how current engagement initiatives impact employee motivation, satisfaction, and commitment, forming the basis for recommendations to improve engagement strategies in the organization.

Table 1: Age

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
25 - 35 years	46	39%
36 - 45 years	26	22%
Above 45 years	26	22%
Below 25	19	16%
Total	117	100%

Source: (primary data compiled through Questionnaire)

Interpretation

The above chart shows that 39% ie,46 respondents fall under the category of age 25-35, 22% ie,26 respondents fall under the category of 36-45, 22% ie,26 respondents fall under the category of age above 45, 16% ie,19 respondents fall under the category of below 25.

Table 2: Gender

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Female	26	22%
Male	91	78%
Total	117	100%

Source: (primary data compiled through Questionnaire)

Interpretation

The above chart shows that 22% ie,26 respondents are female and 78%ie,91 respondents are male.

Table 3: Job positions in the company

Job Position	Frequency	Percentage
Employee	86	74%
Manager	10	9%
Supervisor	21	18%
Total	117	100%

Source: (primary data compiled through Questionnaire)

Interpretation

In the above chart shows that 74% ie, 86 respondents are employees, 9% ie,10 respondents are managers, 18% ie,21 respondents are supervisor.

Table 4: Employee Perception on Organizational Communication and Support

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	64	55%
Agree	43	37%
Neutral	7	6%
Disagree	1	1%
Strongly Disagree	2	2%
Total	117	100%

Source: (primary data compiled through Questionnaire)

Interpretation

The data shows that 55% ie.64 of respondents strongly agree and 37% ie.43 agree that the company communicates effectively and provides adequate support to its employees. Only 6% ie.7 remain neutral, indicating minimal uncertainty or mixed feelings. A very small proportion, 1% ie.1 disagree and 2% ie.2 strongly disagree, suggesting that dissatisfaction regarding communication and support is negligible.

Table 5: Employee experience of work-life balance

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Satisfied	5	4%
Satisfied	79	68%
Neutral	20	17%
Dissatisfied	3	3%
Strongly Dissatisfied	10	9%
Total	117	100%

Source: (primary data compiled through Questionnaire)

Interpretations

The chart shows that the majority of employees, 68% ie,79 employees are satisfied with their work-life balance. A smaller portion, 4% ie,5 employees are strongly satisfied, 17% ie.20 employees are neutral. 3% ie,3 employees are dissatisfied, 9% ie,10 employees are strongly dissatisfied.

Table 6: Employee Perception on Career Growth and Training Opportunities

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very Satisfied	35	30%
Satisfied	53	45%
Neutral	18	15%
Dissatisfied	8	7%
Very Dissatisfied	3	3%
Total	117	100%

Source: (primary data compiled through Questionnaire)

Interpretation

The data shows that 30% ie.35 respondents are very satisfied and 45% ie.53 respondents are satisfied with the career growth and training opportunities provided by the organization. 15% ie.18 respondents remain neutral, while 7% ie.8 respondents are dissatisfied and 3% ie.3 respondents very dissatisfied.

Table 7: Employee Perception on Engagement and Job Satisfaction

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very Satisfied	41	35%
Satisfied	47	40%
Neutral	18	15%
Dissatisfied	8	7%
Very Dissatisfied	3	3%
Total	117	100%

Source: (primary data compiled through Questionnaire)

Interpretation

The data shows that 35% ie.41 respondents are very satisfied and 40% ie.47 respondents are satisfied with their engagement and job satisfaction15% ie.18 respondents remain neutral, while 7% ie.8 respondents are dissatisfied, 3% ie.3 Respondents are very dissatisfied.

Table 8: Employees stress levels at the workplace

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Never	57	49%
Sometimes	42	36%
Often	10	9%
Always	8	7%
Total	117	100%

Interpretation

The data shows that 49% ie,57 employees reported they never feel stressed at work, 36% ie,42 employees experience stress sometimes, 9% ie,10 employees feel stressed often. 7% ie,8 employees, reported feeling stressed always.

6. Findings

Based on the study, the following key findings were observed regarding employee engagement in a small manufacturing company in Dadra and Nagar Haveli (DNH) and Vapi:

- **Age:** 39% of respondents are aged 25–35 years, while the smallest group (16%) is below 25 years.
- **Gender:** 78% of respondents are male, and 22% are female.
- **Job Position:** Majority of respondents are regular employees (74%), followed by supervisors (18%) and managers (9%).
- **Work-Life Balance:** 72% of respondents are satisfied with their work-life balance, while 12% expressed dissatisfaction.
- **Employee Perception on Organizational Communication and Support:** A majority of respondents (92%) agree that the company communicates effectively and provides adequate support to employees, while only 3% express disagreement.
- **Employee Perception on Career Growth and Training Opportunities:** Most respondents (75%) are satisfied with the career growth and training opportunities provided by the organization, while only 10% express dissatisfaction.
- **Employee Perception on Engagement and Job Satisfaction:** A majority of respondents (75%) are satisfied with their engagement and job satisfaction, while only 10% express dissatisfaction.
- **Employees stress levels at the workplace:** Most employees (85%) experience little to occasional stress at work, while only 7% report feeling stressed always.

7. Recommendations

Source: Self Developed Model based on the study and observation

This Model on Employee Engagement is based on four main factors - **Involvement, Leadership, Communication, and Commitment.**

- **Involvement** means how actively employees take part in their work and contribute to the organization’s goals.
- **Leadership** shows how supportive and motivating leaders help employees perform better and feel valued.
- **Communication** focuses on open and clear sharing of information between management and employees.
- **Commitment** represents employees’ loyalty and emotional connection with the organization.

All these four factors together explain how engaged the employees are in their work and how these aspects affect their satisfaction and performance.

8. Conclusion

The study highlights the critical role of employee engagement in enhancing organizational performance and employee satisfaction. Findings indicate that while employees are generally satisfied with the company’s engagement practices, improvements are needed in areas such as recognition, communication, and career development. This research has provided practical insights into employee engagement and underscored the importance of continuous improvement in HR practices to maintain a motivated and satisfied workforce.

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